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METHANOLIC LEAF EXTRACT OF *VENTILAGO MADERASPATANA* AMELIORATION OF OXIDATIVE STRESS INDUCED LIVER DAMAGE UNDER DIABETIC CONDITION IN ALBINO RATS

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the present study was to investigate the effect of methanolic leaf extract of *Ventilago maderaspatana* (MEVML, 200mg/kg b.w.) on oxidative stress markers in the diabetic rat liver. Diabetes exacerbates hepatic injury induced by STZ delivered free radical mediated oxidative stress. A marked decreased in the anti-oxidant marker enzymes, superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), glutathione peroxidase (GPx), glutathione reductase (GR) and increase in malondialdehyde (MDA) was observed in the diabetic rats. Decreased activities of anti-oxidant enzymes in diabetic rats were augmented on oral administration of MEVML. Moreover, MEVML administration depleted the MDA level, which was earlier increased in the diabetic rats. These results suggest that MEVML exhibit a hepatoprotective effect by accelerating hepatic anti-oxidant defense mechanisms and down regulating the MDA levels to the normal levels in the diabetic rats. Thus, MEVML may be used as therapeutic agent in preventing complications in diabetic patients.

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INTRODUCTION

It is well known that the incidence of diabetes mellitus is high all over the world, especially in Asia. Different types of oral hypoglycaemic agents such as biguanides and sulphonylurea are available along with insulin for the treatment of diabetes mellitus [1], but have side effects associated with their uses [2, 3]. There is a growing interest in herbal remedies because of their effectiveness, minimal side effects in clinical experience and relatively low costs. Herbal drugs or their extracts are prescribed widely, even when their biological active compounds are unknown. Even the World Health Organization (WHO) approves the use of plant drugs for different diseases, including diabetes mellitus. Therefore, studies with plant extracts are useful to know their efficacy and mechanism of action and safety. Medicinal plants useful in diabetes were reviewed recently [4, 5].

Traditionally *Ventilago maderaspatana* plant has been widely used for treating various diseases such as Diabetes [6], Stomach disorders [7], Hepatitis etc. And also, additionally this plant has wound healing, analgesic, anti-ulcer, antioxidant [8], diuretic [9], anti-inflammatory and antibacterial properties [10]. However, MEVML has not revealed the hepatoprotective activity under diabetic condition not yet now. Thus the present study is investigated the convalescence of diabetic induced oxidative damage in liver tissue by treatment with MEVML in rats.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Animals

Wistar strain of rats, weighing about 180 ± 20 g used in the experiments. Animals were kept in our animal house at an ambient temperature of 25°C with 12 h each of dark and light cycles. Animals were fed pellet diet of Sai Durga feed, Bangalore and water ad-libitum. For experimental purpose the animals were kept fasting overnight but were allowed free access to water. The experiments were carried out in accordance with guidelines and protocol approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (Regd. No. 488/01/a/CPCSEA/dt.17.072001).

Chemicals

STZ was obtained from Sigma chemicals (USA). All the other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Induction of diabetes

The animals were fasted overnight and diabetes was induced by a single intraperitoneally injection of a freshly prepared solution of streptozotocin (STZ) (50 mg/kg body weight) in 0.1 M cold citrate buffer (pH 4.5). The animals were considered as diabetic, if their blood glucose values were above 250 mg/dl on the third day after STZ injection curcumin treatment was given to the diabetic rats for 30 days.

Grouping of animals

The rats were divided into five groups, six rats in each group and treated as follows:

Group 1. Normal control (NC): This group of rats received 0.9% NaCl solution.

Group 2. Diabetic Control (STZ 50mg/kg body weight) (DC): Streptozotocin was given 50mg/kg.b.w intraperitoneally for the induction of diabetes to this group.

Group 3: Methanaloic extract of *Ventilago maderaspatana* leaves (MEVML,200mg/kg b.w.) control (PC) : Six rats received with MEVML a dose of 200 mg/kg body weight via oral gavage for 30 days.

Group 4. Diabetic +glibenclamide treatment (Di + Glib): Diabetic rats treated with glibenclamide 20 mg/kg body weight orally.

Group 5. Diabetic + Curcumin treatment (Di + Ct): Diabetic rats received MEVML (200 mg/kg) for a period of 30 days

After completion of 30days treatment the animals were sacrificed by cervical dislocation and the liver tissues were excised at 4°C . The tissues were washed with ice-cold saline, immersed in liquid nitrogen and immediately stored at -80°C for further biochemical analysis.

Analytical procedures

Assessment of Oxidative Stress Marker

Superoxide dismutase (SOD):

Superoxide dismutase activity was determined according to the method [11] at room temperature. The Liver tissue was homogenized in ice cold 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) containing 0.1 mM EDTA to give 5% homogenate (w/v). The homogenates were centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 min at 4°C in ice cold centrifuge. The supernatant was separated and used for enzyme assay. 100 μl of tissue extract was added to 880 μl (0.05 M, P^{H} 10.2, containing 0.1 mM EDTA) carbonate buffer and 20 μl of 30 mM epinephrine (in 0.05% acetic acid) was added to the mixture and measured the optical density values at 480 nm for 4 min on a Hitachi U-2000 Spectrophotometer. Activity expressed as the amount of enzyme that inhibits the oxidation of epinephrine by 50%, which is equal to 1-unit activity.

Catalase (CAT) :

Catalase activity was measured by a slightly modified version [12] at room temperature. The Liver was homogenized in ice cold 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) containing 0.1 mM EDTA to give 5% homogenate (w/v). The homogenates were centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 min at 4^oC in ice cold centrifuge. The resulting supernatant was used as enzyme source. 10 µl of 100% ethyl alcohol was added to 100 µl of tissue extract and then placed in an ice bath for 30 min. After 30 minutes the tubes were kept at room temperature followed by the addition of 10 µl of Triton X-100 RS. In a cuvette containing 200 µl of phosphate buffer and 50 µl of tissue extract was added 250 µl of 0.066 M H₂O₂ (in phosphate buffer) was added and decrease in optical density measured at 240 nm for 60 s in a UV Spectrophotometer. The molar extinction coefficient of 43.6 M cm⁻¹ was used to determine CAT activity. One unit activity is equal to the moles of H₂O₂ degraded / mg protein / min.

Glutathione Peroxidase (GPx):

Glutathione Peroxidase (GPx) was determined by a modified version [13] at 37^oC. 5% (w/v) of Liver tissue homogenate was prepared in 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) containing 0.1 mM EDTA. The homogenate were centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10min at 0^oC in ice cold centrifuge. The resulting supernatant was used as enzyme source. The Reaction mixture consisted of 500 µl of phosphate buffer, 100 µl of 0.01 M GSH (reduced form), 100 µl of 1.5 mM NADPH and 100 µl of GR (0.24 units). 100 µl of tissue extract was added to the reaction mixture and incubated at 37^oC for 10 min. Then 50 µl of 12 mM t-butyl hydroperoxide was added to 450 µl of tissue reaction mixture and the colour developed was measured at 340 nm for 180 s. The molar extinction coefficient of 6.22 X 10³ M cm⁻¹ was used to determine the activity. One unit of activity is equal to the mM of NADPH oxidized / mg protein / min. The enzyme activity was expressed in µmoles of NADPH oxidized / mg protein / min.

Glutathione Reductase (GR):

Slightly modified method [14] was used for the estimation of Glutathione reductase activity at 37^oC. 5% of liver tissue homogenized in 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) containing 0.1 mM EDTA then it was centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10min at 0^oC in ice cold centrifuge. The supernatant part(100 µl) was used as enzyme source. and it was added to NADPH-GSSG solution which contains NADPH (50 µl, 2mM) in 10mM Tris buffer (pH 7.0) 50 µl of GSSG (20mM) in phosphate buffer (0.5 M, pH 7.0 containing 0.1 mM EDTA) and 800 µl of phosphate buffer. and measured at 340 nm for 3 min. The enzyme activity was expressed in µ moles of NADPH oxidized / mg protein / min.

Assessment of oxidative tissue damage markers**MDA content (Lipid Peroxidation) in liver tissue:**

MDA levels determine [15]. 5% of liver tissue was homogenized (- w/v) in 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) containing 0.1 mM EDTA and centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 min at 0^oC in cold centrifuge. 200 µl of supernatant was added to 50 µl of 8.1% sodium dodecyle sulphate vortexed and incubated for 10 min at room temperature. 375 µl of twenty percent acetic acid (pH 3.5) and 375 µl of thiobarbituric acid (0.6%) were added and kept in boiling water bath for 60 min and allowed cool at room temperature. Then 1.25 ml of butanol: pyridine (15:1)mixer was added, vortexed and centrifuged at 1000 rpm for 5 min. The colored was measured at 532 nm.

RESULTS**Effect of MEVML on oxidative stress markers****Effect of MEVML on SOD activity:**

In the present study, the activity of superoxide dismutase (SOD) was measured in liver of all the experimental groups such as Normal control (NC), Diabetic control (DC), Normal + MEVML treated (N+PC), Glibenclamide + Diabetes (Di+GLB) and Diabetes + MEVML treated (Di+Pt).A substantial decrease in the activity of SOD in the liver tissue has been noticed during diabetic condition.Increased the activity of SOD in diabetic rats when treated with MEVML and Glibenclamide which shown in Fig.1.

Effect of MEVML on CAT activity

The activity of Catalase was determined in the liver of all experimental rats such as Normal control (NC), Diabetic control (DC), Normal + Methanolic leaf extraction of *Ventilago maderaspatana* (MEVML) treated (N+PC), Glibenclamide+ Diabetes (Di+GLB) and Diabetes + MEVML treated (Di+Pt). Catalase activity in liver tissue was significantly reduced in diabetic rats. When treated diabetic rats with methanolic leaf extraction of *Ventilago maderaspatana* and Glibenclamide enhance the catalase activity shown in Fig-2

Effect of MEVML on GPx activity

GPx activity was measured in the liver of all experimental rats such as Normal control (NC), Diabetic control (DC), Normal + MEVML treated (N+PC), Glibenclamide+ Diabetes (Di+GLB) and Diabetes + MEVML treated (Di+Pt).Glutathione Peroxidase activity is significantly reduced in liver tissue of diabetic rats. When treated with Methanolic leaf extraction of *Ventilago maderaspatana* and Glibenclamide shows an improvement of glutathione peroxidase activity shown in Fig-3

Effect of MEVML on GR activity

The activity of glutathione reductase was determined in the liver tissue of all experimental rats such as Normal control (NC), Diabetic control (DC), Normal + MEVML treated (N+PC), Glibenclamide + Diabetes (Di+GLB) and Diabetes + MEVML

treated (Di+Pt). Glutathione Reductase activity is significantly reduced in liver tissue of diabetic rats. When treated with MEVML and Glibenclamide glutathione reductase activity was increased in diabetic rats shown in Fig-4.

Effect of MEVML on oxidative tissue damage marker

Effect of MEVML on MDA

Lipid peroxidation activity was measured in the liver tissue of all experimental rats such as Normal control (NC), Diabetic control (DC), Normal + MEVML treated (N+PC), Glibenclamide+ Diabetes (Di+GLB) and Diabetes + MEVML treated (Di+Pt). MDA activity is significantly increased in liver tissue of diabetic rats. When treated with Methanolic leaf extraction of *Ventilago maderaspatana* and Glibenclamide shows decrease in MDA activity shown in Fig-5

DISCUSSION

Diabetes is possibly the world's fastest growing metabolic disease, and as knowledge of the heterogeneity of this disorder increases, so does the need for more appropriate therapies [1, 2]. Currently, available drug regimens for management of diabetes have certain drawbacks such as vascular complications, hepato toxicity, cardio toxicity and neuronal toxicity.

Management of diabetes with the agents devoid of any side effects is still a challenge to the medical system. This has led to an increase in the demand for natural products with anti-hyperglycaemic activity and fewer side effects. Traditional plant medicines are used throughout the world for a range of diabetic conditions. The study of such medicines might offer a natural key to unlock a diabetologist's pharmacy for the future [4]. Diabetes is associated with a higher oxidative stress. ROS induced damage to the insulin-producing pancreatic beta-cells induces diabetes. Anti-oxidant therapy involving the use of herbs and spices has been shown to protect the tissues against such damage. It has been shown that under physiological conditions glucose may undergo auto-oxidation and contribute to ROS formation [5]. Diabetes induced oxidative damage is responsible for the changes occurring in the activities of anti-oxidant enzymes leading to impaired hepatic activity. Streptozotocin injection resulted in diabetes mellitus, which may be due to destruction of beta cells of Islets of Langerhans as proposed by others [4,5]. Diabetes arises from irreversible destruction of pancreatic beta cells, causing degranulation and reduction of insulin secretion [2,3]. STZ-induced diabetes is characterized by a severe loss in body weight [16] and may exhibit most of the diabetic complications such as, myocardial, cardiovascular, nervous, kidney and urinary bladder dysfunction through oxidative stress [17].

Oxidative stress is the imbalance between production and removal of reactive oxygen species. Increased oxidative stress, which contributes substantially to the pathogenesis of diabetic complications, is the consequences of either enhanced ROS production or attenuated ROS scavenging capacity. Several reports have shown the alterations in the anti-oxidant enzymes during diabetic condition [18]

The endogenous antioxidant enzymes such as SOD, CAT and GPx are responsible for the detoxification of deleterious oxygen radicals. SOD has been postulated as one of the most important enzymes in the enzymatic antioxidant defense system which catalyses the dismutation of superoxide radicals to produce H₂O₂ and molecular oxygen hence diminishing the toxic effects caused by these radicals [19]. Catalase (CAT) is a heme protein which catalyses the reduction of hydrogen peroxides and protects the tissues from highly reactive hydroxyl radicals. GPx plays a primary role in minimizing oxidative damage. It has been proposed that GPx is responsible for the detoxification of H₂O₂ in low concentration whereas catalase comes into play when GPx pathway is reaching saturation with the substrate. GPx catalyze the reduction of hydrogen peroxide and hydroperoxides to non-toxic metabolites [20]. The reduction in SOD and catalase activities in diabetic condition may be due to direct glycation of enzyme protein [21]. The increase in superoxide radical in diabetes may inhibit the activity of catalase and glutathione peroxidase [22]. GPx function is concert with GSH in decomposing hydrogen peroxide generated from free radical mediated reactions. Due to decrease in the concentration of GSH, the activity of GPx is also decreased in diabetes [23]. The diminished activity of GPx in diabetes elevates hydrogen peroxide and lipid peroxides leading to the accumulation of these oxidants and thus the subsequent oxidation of lipids. It has been concluded that the restoration of antioxidant defense system by the administration of MEVML under diabetic condition may be attributed mainly due to the presence of antioxidant phytochemical [24,25].

The tremendous increase in TBARS and hydroperoxides in liver tissues suggests an increase in oxygen radicals that could be due to either increased production or decreased detoxification under hyperglycemia in diabetes [26]. Maintenance of persistent antioxidant enzymes activity by the administration of MEVML attenuated the lipid peroxidation in tissues and thus prevents tissue damage [27].

Fig-1: Changes in SOD activity in Liver of Normal control (NC), Diabetic control (DC), Normal + MEVML (PC), Diabetes + Glibenclamide (Di+ GLB), Diabetes + MEVML (Di+ Pt) treated rats. Data mean \pm SD values (n=6). The groups that do not share same letters are significant ($P < 0.05$) to the control.

Fig-2: Changes in CAT activity in Liver of Normal control (NC), Diabetic control (DC), Normal + MEVML (PC), Diabetes + Glibenclamide (Di+ GLB), Diabetes + MEVML (Di+ Pt) treated rats. Data mean \pm SD values (n=6). The groups that do not share same letters are significant ($P < 0.05$) to the control.

Fig-3: Changes in GPx activity in Liver of Normal control (NC), Diabetic control (DC), Normal + MEVML (PC), Diabetes + Glibenclamide (Di+ GLB), Diabetes + MEVML (Di+ Pt) treated rats. Data mean ± SD values (n=6). The groups that do not share same letters are significant (P<0.05) to the control.

Fig-4: Changes in GR activity in Liver of Normal control (NC), Diabetic control (DC), Normal + MEVML (PC), Diabetes + Glibenclamide (Di+ GLB), Diabetes + MEVML (Di+ Pt) treated rats. Data mean ± SD values (n=6). The groups that do not share same letters are significant (P<0.05) to the control.

Fig-5: Changes in MDA levels in Liver of Normal control (NC), Diabetic control (DC), Normal + MEVML (PC), Diabetes + Glibenclamide (Di+ GLB), Diabetes + MEVML (Di+ Pt) treated rats. Data mean \pm SD values (n=6). The groups that do not share same letters are significant ($P < 0.05$) to the control.

CONCLUSION

From the results of the present study it may be concluded that the antidiabetic and antioxidant nature of MEVML might be due to the presence of biologically active phytochemicals present in the extract. Further, the present study demonstrates the scientific rationale for the use of MEVML in the traditional medicine for the treatment of diabetes.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None

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